

End to End Hierarchical Network Orchestration Using Transport API

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Abstract— Transport SDN is becoming a reality where network operators use multiple controllers in order to obtain multi-vendor interoperability. With this purpose, ONF Transport API has been proposed as a transport SDN controller northbound interface towards transport applications and services (e.g., NMS, parent controllers, NFV MANO).

In this paper, we present the results of the Transport API multi-vendor multi-domain interoperability tests with a hierarchical orchestration layer. The demonstration shows the end-to-end provision of connections based on the topology and connectivity services of the ONF Transport API.

Keywords—Transport API, ONF, orchestration, hierarchical control and management, SDN.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network operators have been claiming their will towards multi-vendor interoperability in transport networks. Interoperability demonstrations help to align the proposed solutions of the equipment manufacturers (vendors), while creating a competitive environment that fosters innovation and leads to new developments and product evolution. The

definition of the Transport API (TAPI) within the Open Networking Foundation (ONF) is a pragmatic approach to obtain an end-to-end (E2E) Software Defined Network (SDN) infrastructure for transport networks. It supports network programmability in each optical domain without requiring full data plane interoperability. Multi-layer/domain SDN will enable many innovative use cases which will lead to new service product offerings and business opportunities like multi-tenancy, bandwidth on demand, and data center workload balancing. However, network operators also plan to automate today's internal operational processes like multi-layer network optimization, multi-domain link configuration and restoration through SDN. Currently, network operators deploy optical networks on a regional basis. This means that each vendor uses its technology in a given area and operates it, which is very relevant for production environments. The use of the TAPI as a North-Bound Interface (NBI) of the optical controllers allows the utilization of a common information model to support the optical services. This work has been done within the umbrella of the Optical Internetworking Forum (OIF) to coordinate industry in this interworking activity.

The SDN/NFV orchestration architecture [1] is represented in Fig. 1. The application layer contains the cloud orchestrator, which is in charge of providing compute storage and network resources for NFV Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). The VNFs may be located on the same data-center or they can be distributed within the network. In order to provide end-to-end connectivity for data-center interconnection (DCI), set-up of end-to-end service is required across a multi-vendor, multi-domain environment. The control layer is composed by the Network Orchestrator (also known as multi-domain SDN controller) and the SDN controllers. The network orchestrator is defined as a parent controller or a centralized “controller of controllers”, which handles the automation of end-to-end connectivity provisioning, working at a higher, abstracted level and covering inter-domain aspects. The controller is defined as an entity that is in charge of the specifics of the underlying technology. The TAPI is the interface for the control layer. It provides a common abstraction model between the controllers and the orchestrator.

Fig. 1 SDN/NFV orchestration architecture for multi-vendor optical transport networks with hierarchical orchestrators

Finally, the infrastructure layer has the Network Elements (NEs) which is the L1/L0 equipment of the different vendors.

This paper extends the demonstration performed at OFC 2017 [2], by providing the details of the different use cases and their results, which have been demonstrated in Telefónica Labs, Madrid (Spain). The paper is organized as follows. Firstly, an introduction to ONF Transport API is provided. Then, E2E hierarchical network orchestration is discussed. Later, the demonstrated use cases are presented. In section V, the experimental results are presented and discussed and finally, in section VI conclusions are provided.

II. TRANSPORT API

The TAPI abstracts the main services for an SDN controller: (1) Network Topology, (2) Connectivity Requests, (3) Path Computation, (4) Network Virtualization, and (5) Notification. Network Topology functionality requires, at a minimum, that the interface exports the context (Fig.2), which is the scope of control, interaction and naming that a particular TAPI provider (SDN controller) or client application has with respect to the

information exchanged over the interface. The context describes the Service End Points, which refer to the outward customer-facing aspects of the edge-port functions, and the Network Topology. However, network identifiers help to carry out path computation and to integrate the nodes for an end-to-end scenario. Further, the controllers can provide information about the links and nodes in the domain (complete or abstracted, depending on the configured shared context). It is clear that the more information is shared, the less abstracted the network appears. The Connectivity Service represents an “intent-like” request for connectivity between two or more Service-End-Points. Instead, a connection is the provisioned potential for forwarding (circuit/packet) between two or more Node Edge Points of a Node. However, there are other Connectivity Constraints that can be requested, such as (a) excluding or including nodes/links for traffic engineering, (b) defining the protection level, (c) defining its bandwidth or (d) defining its disjointness from another connection.

The Path Computation function is a critical and fundamental feature because individual controllers in each domain are only able to share abstracted information that is local to their domain. An orchestrator with its global end-to-end view can optimize end-to-end connections that individual controllers cannot configure.

Network Virtualization services enables to expose a subset of the network resources to different tenants.

Finally, a Notification service allows a publish and subscribe mechanism, which will allow asynchronous notifications using a protocol such as websockets.

In view of this, we can affirm that the TAPI is in a good position to be the NBI of the SDN orchestrator or as the common abstraction model between the SDN orchestrator and the controllers. The importance of TAPI relays in its simplicity and usability in order to extend its adoption. Other solutions based on YANG models are being proposed in the scope of IETF and OpenConfig.

III. E2E HIERARCHICAL NETWORK ORCHESTRATION

This work demonstrates the use of TAPI to support end-to-end interoperability with a hierarchical orchestration layer through the collaboration of the ONF/OIF. The demonstration shows end-to-end provisioning of connections based on the topology and connectivity services of the TAPI. A first milestone towards this concept was the presentation of the first OIF/ONF interoperability event Global Transport SDN Prototype Demonstration [3], where a REST interface was proposed for Service Request API. There is also previous work within the research community. The EU-Japan STRAUSS project proposed a multi-domain SDN architecture where the network orchestrator acted as a unified transport network control layer, which enables end-to-end resources orchestration across multiple domains with heterogeneous technologies [4]. The authors in [5] demonstrated a network orchestrator provisioning end-to-end optical services with SDN controllers, but without any common interface. Therefore, the work in [5] lacked a standard interface to operate the optical domains. Based on this need, the authors in [6] proposed the utilization of a Common Orchestration Protocol (COP), which provides a

research-oriented multi-technology approach using YANG/RESTconf [7]. This research work was taken as a basis to define the functional requirements of the ONF TAPI [8]. The first demonstration of the TAPI within a single domain scenario was done in [9], including the Snowmass Open Source code for a reference implementation in [10].

The main contribution of this work is the experimental demonstration of end-to-end provisioning using an SDN/NFV architecture across multiple control domains using the TAPI to retrieve topology and set-up multi-domain connections. This experiment is done using commercial SDN products from very relevant players in the industry, which are co-authoring this work. It demonstrates that SDN is ready for abstracted control of optical networks, once the deployments of the vendors are moved to a commercial version of implementation. A secondary contribution is the utilization of a hierarchical architecture, which enables other use cases for operators like network slicing or bandwidth on demand. The hierarchical architecture for SDN control domains has been presented in [11]. The authors propose hierarchical SDN Orchestration to handle SDN network orchestration scalability and security. A parent/child SDN Orchestrator architecture based on Applications-Based Network Operations (ABNO) was proposed and experimentally validated.

Fig. 2 Lab infrastructure to support the demonstration

The demonstration will show how the orchestrators are able to obtain the topology information of the SDN controllers at different levels of abstraction. The top orchestrator will carry out end-to-end provisioning of optical connections to provide services to end customers, which are connected behind an IP router. The set-up is composed of five optical controllers and two multi-domain orchestrators (MDO). Fig. 2 shows the hierarchical relationship between the parent MDO and child MDO. The data plane connectivity will be validated to see how capacity service is set-up across the multiple domains.

IV. PROPOSED USE CASES

In this section, we describe three different use cases where hierarchical control is demonstrated with the use of TAPI. Firstly, we present multi-domain topology discovery, which may make use of network abstraction or provide full topology visibility. Secondly, we present unconstrained multi-domain provisioning. Finally, we present how to include multi-domain constraints, such as diversity, link/node inclusion or exclusion, latency and cost.

A. TAPI usage for multi-domain topology discovery

This proposed use case is the basis for control and management of multi-domain network, as it is the necessary step for topology discovery across several control domains. Several assumptions have been proposed, such as the consideration of multiple control domains within a single carrier domain and, domains might expose all the topological information or partially abstract it.

Fig. 3 Abstracted network hierarchical topology

Fig. 3 shows the abstracted topology exposed by the child MDO (cMDO) towards its parent MDO (pMDO). Several abstraction methods have been proposed in literature [12]. The proposed method in this scenario is edge-based abstraction, where each network edge is provided as an abstracted node and the virtual links between the network edges are offered. The cMDO is the responsible for providing this abstracted topology.

The objective of this use case is to demonstrate how topology is discovered by both pMDO and cMDO. Moreover, each MDO will need to understand how the domains are connected together and to infer multi-domain connections. Finally, each MDO provides the MD topology to its applications (i.e., end applications or pMDO).

This use case follows the next steps: a) Multi-domain orchestrators (MDO) discover each domain topology and Service End Points and Node Edge Points over TAPI; b) MDOs learn about cross-domain connectivity; c) MDOs put the different parts into a coherent MD model.

Fig. 4 Hierarchical topology at the parent MDO

Fig. 4 shows the constructed MD topology at the parent MDO. It can be observed how cMDO abstracts its underlying domains, and how multi-domain links are constructed with the usage of Service End Points (SEP).

B. Unconstrained Multi-domain Provisioning

The next use case proposes to set up a connection across multiple optical domains without any restriction, as shown in Fig. 5.

The workflow is as follows. A connectivity service creation request is received by pMDO via an application (e.g., NMS, NFV orchestrator). The connectivity service provides no constraints, but the necessary service ports, which provide references to the offered SEP.

The pMDO computes an optimal MD path for the received request and the obtained MD topology (which might be partially abstracted). The pMDO asks each of the underlying controllers for a connectivity service creation. If the underlying controller is a cMDO, this hierarchical process will be recursively applied, until all domain controllers are reached. If all controllers reply positively, the pMDO sets up a connection for the original connectivity service request. Otherwise, MDO considers a different MD path.

Fig. 5 Unconstrained MD connectivity service provisioning

C. Constrained Multi-domain Provisioning

This use case focuses on the different possibilities to offer connectivity services across multiple optical domains subject to various constraints, such as diversity, exclude/include link/node, latency, and/or costs. The MDO shall be able to avoid infeasible paths or paths that do not comply with the constraints.

The Transport API allows several connectivity service constraints, which can be interpreted as intents, and the MDO is responsible for allocating the resources that fulfill the maximum number of constraints. Such constraints are the following: service type and level, preferred transport layer, requested capacity, cost, latency, co-route inclusion, diversity exclusion, include/avoid topology/path/route. Several sub-scenarios have been proposed such as: Minimum cost path in each single domain, Single domain diversity and MD diversity (as showed in Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Connectivity service provisioning with MD diversity

Once a connectivity service request is received by MDO, it computes an optimal MD path for the request that complies with the constraints. MDO asks each of the domain controllers for a connectivity service with the pertinent constraints. If all controllers reply positively, MDO sets up a path. Otherwise, MDO considers a different MD path.

V. EXPERIMENTAL DEMONSTRATION

The authors successfully demonstrated interoperability in Telefónica laboratories, as published in [13]. During the interoperability tests, the different presented use cases involving hierarchical control were demonstrated.

The development of TAPI has followed an agile process as described in Fig. 7. From uses cases and requirements, the CIM has been pruned and refactored in a TAPI UML information model, which has been used as an input to automatic translation tools in order to obtain TAPI YANG schemas. These have been automatically translated into Swagger API descriptions that have allowed the development of a TAPI reference implementation in OSSDN project Snowmass.

Fig. 7 TAPI components and related projects

In order to demonstrate the presented use cases, firstly we focus on the demonstration of hierarchical topological recovery and MD topological view construction. To this end, the pMDO requests a GET REST message for topology towards its underlying SDN controllers and cMDO. The cMDO recursively requests the topology towards its underlying SDN controllers. Finally, the pMDO obtains the underlying

topological descriptions in order to compose its own MD topological view.

Fig. 8 shows a topology JSON object obtained between the cMDO and an SDN controller. It can be observed that `_node` and `_link` array objects are the most significant contained in the JSON object. A node includes the owned Node Edge Points (NEP), among other necessary modeling parameters. A link includes the list of link ports, which includes references to NEPs.

Fig. 8 Wireshark Topology JSON example

In order to validate unconstrained MD Provisioning, we proceed to create a Connectivity Service request (POST) towards the NBI of pMDO. This action triggered a MD path computation, which selected the necessary involved control domains. In Fig. 9, we can observe the request from the pMDO towards the cMDO. This connectivity service request triggers connectivity service requests towards SDN controllers, and once succeeded the original connectivity service creation is acknowledged.

pMDO	cMDO	HTTP	943	POST	/restconf/config/Context/_connectivityService	HTTP/1.1	(application/json)
cMDO	SDN_CTL1	HTTP	779	POST	/restconf/config/Context/_connectivityService	HTTP/1.1	(application/json)
SDN_CTL1	cMDO	HTTP	1211	HTTP/1.1	200 OK	(application/json)	
cMDO	SDN_CTL2	HTTP	562	POST	/restconf/config/Context/_connectivityService/	HTTP/1.1	(application/json)
SDN_CTL2	cMDO	HTTP	818	HTTP/1.1	201 Created	(application/json)	
cMDO	pMDO	HTTP	918	HTTP/1.1	200 OK	(application/json)	

Fig. 9 Wireshark Connectivity Service message exchange

In order to demonstrate the constrained MD provisioning use case, we create a constrained connectivity service request towards the pMDO. Once received, the pMDO performs a constrained MD shortest path allocation algorithm in order to determine the involved control domains. Once computed, the constraints are incorporated in the connectivity service request of the involved SDN controllers and cMDO. Fig. 10 shows any example of connectivity service creation request. It includes the involved SEP references, as well as the requested connectivity constraints. In this figure we can observe service type, requested capacity and service layer constraints. We have exercised other available TAPI connectivity constraints such as

latency, co-route inclusion, diversity exclusion, and include path.

Fig. 10 Wireshark Connectivity Service JSON object

VI. CONCLUSIONS

SDN/NFV topics are very relevant for the optical community and will lead to new service product offerings and business opportunities for network operators. The view of the optical network as a static and dumb infrastructure is not acceptable any longer. This demonstration is relevant to see the collaboration of research, standardization fora and industry. This work extends research initiatives, which started within 2014, with innovation from research and industrial institutions.

This work is done with the support of the ONF/OIF. The ONF started a new collaboration model based on Open Source initiatives like the Snowmass project [10]. The utilization of Open Source reduces the time to creation of a testing environment like the one used by OIF. The relevance of this new way to carry out standardization is very attractive. The industry needs specifications to define the requirements of the solutions and develop the products, while, on the other hand, Open Source projects facilitate a dynamic environment, where research institutions, like CTTC in this case, can provide a reference implementation that is then improved on by the industry.

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